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Discovery of a large Ordovician sedimentary burial slab in the vicinity of the Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland

Tomasz Borowski

The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin,
Złocieniec, District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

E-mail address: tomasz.elvis.borowski@wp.pl
ORCID: 0000-0002-2600-2739

ABSTRACT

This article presents the discovery of a large Ordovician sedimentary burial slab located on the grounds of the Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo in the West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland. The dimensions of this Ordovician slab are as follows: length—155 cm, width—105 cm, and thickness—20 cm. The slab weighs 380 kg. Fossilised animal species were discovered and documented through photographs on the surface of this Ordovician sedimentary slab, including cephalopods of the genera *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789, and *Lituities* Bertrand, 1763, as well as trilobites of the genus *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827. Currently, this Ordovician find is housed at the Stone Museum in Kamień Pomorski, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland.

Keywords: Ordovician sedimentary burial slab, cephalopods, *Orthoceras*, *Lituities*, trilobites, *Illaneus*, Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, animal fossils

1. INTRODUCTION

In the Central Pomerania region of north-western Poland, typical post-glacial deposits date from the last Scandinavian glaciation, approximately 11,000 years ago (Map 1) [1].

Map 3. Location of the Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland. (53°29'19.7"N 15°36'57.2"E) (Google Maps).

Currently, there are many mineral resource mines in this area, including the Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland (Maps 2 and 3, Photo 1). This mine extracts and sorts fine- and coarse-grained sand and gravel for general construction purposes (Photos 2–4).

During the extraction of mineral resources, many small and medium-sized stones, as well as typical large glacial erratics, are left behind. From time to time, Ordovician glacial sedimentary stones can be observed in the mine; these are not processed due to their low hardness and high friability.

Not always, but occasionally, Ordovician sedimentary stones contain animal fossils such as nautiluses, trilobites, shellfish and snails. Fossils of corals are also very rarely found in the mine. These are corals of the genera *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816 and *Halysites* Fischer von Waldheim, 1828 [2].

2. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In 2019, a large Ordovician sedimentary burial slab was discovered in the vicinity of the Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland (Photo 5). This slab was found buried deep in the ground on a slope within the mine site.

In May 2026, a team was organised to excavate and transport the Ordovician find to the Museum of Stones in Kamień Pomorski, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, where it is currently housed.

Photographs 6 and 7 show the excavated Ordovician burial slab, measuring 155 cm in length, 105 cm in width, and 20 cm in thickness. The total weight of this slab is 380 kg.

Photograph 8 shows the site where the Ordovician slab was previously located.

Animal fossils were discovered on this Ordovician slab and documented in photographs:

- ✓ *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789 (Photos 9-11, 13) [3-8],
- ✓ *Lituites* Bertrand, 1763 (Photo 12) [9-13],
- ✓ *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827 (Photos 13-15) [14-16].

Due to the size and weight of the Ordovician burial slab, a team of museum staff transported the excavated slab on steel rollers to a vehicle, from where it was taken to the Museum of Stones in Kamień Pomorski.

Photographs 16–19 show the traditional method of moving the Ordovician slab on steel rollers from the site of discovery to the vehicle. It took five hours to move the slab by 300 metres.

Photo 20 shows the discoverer, Tomasz Borowski, with the Ordovician slab ready for transport by vehicle. All photographs in this article were taken by the author, Tomasz Borowski.

3. CONCLUSION

The mineral mines in the Central Pomerania region undoubtedly still harbour many undiscovered fossils that bear witness to the evolution of the geology of the region and the animal life that once thrived there.

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Documentation of Photos

Photo 1. Photo 1. The Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland (2026).

Photo 2. The area around the Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland (2026).

Photo 3. The area around the Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland (2026).

Photo 4. The area around the Mineral Resources Production Plant Storkowo, West Pomeranian Voivodeship, Poland (2026).

Photo 5. The discovery of an Ordovician sedimentary burial slab in 2019 on the site of a Storkowo mine.

Photo 6. Photo 6. Ordovician sedimentary burial slab (2026).

Photo 7. Ordovician sedimentary burial slab (2026).

Photo 8. The site, after the Ordovician sedimentary burial slab had been excavated (2026).

Photo 9. *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789.

Photo 10. *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789.

Photo 11. *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789.

Photo 12. *Lituites* Bertrand, 1763.

Photo 13. *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789 and *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827.

Photo 14. *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827.

Photo 15. *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827.

Photo 16. The traditional method of moving the Ordovician slab on steel rollers from its point of discovery to the vehicle (2026).

Photo 17. The traditional method of moving the Ordovician slab on steel rollers from its point of discovery to the vehicle (2026).

Photo 18. The traditional method of moving the Ordovician slab on steel rollers from its point of discovery to the vehicle (2026).

Photo 19. The traditional method of moving the Ordovician slab on steel rollers from its point of discovery to the vehicle (2026).

Photo 20. Tomasz Borowski, the discoverer, alongside the Ordovician sedimentary burial slab (2026).